

Educational Leadership and Management Strategies Views of the Lens of Public School Teachers

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Abstract. This qualitative inquiry aimed to unravel the multifaceted aspects of leadership and management practices impacting classroom dynamics, teacher motivation, and student achievement. The study focused on fourteen (14) high school teachers from Crossing Bayabas National High School, delving into their adaptive leadership practices, management strategies for classroom dynamics, professional development's influence on leadership, and the direct correlation between leadership and student outcomes. Thematic analysis illuminated the coping mechanisms employed by teachers, emphasizing resource utilization, adaptation, impact, and teacher well-being when faced with challenges related to implementing leadership and management practices. Insights from teachers' encounters with these practices highlighted the evolution of pedagogical perspectives, enhanced reflective teaching, and the cultivation of collaborative learning environments. Implementing these insights entails tailored professional development programs for teachers, fostering reflective practices through mentorship, and redesigning classroom setups to promote collaboration. By incorporating these implications into its educational management practices, Crossing Bayabas National High School could create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment, ultimately enhancing student learning experiences and outcomes. These findings hold immense implications for education stakeholders, including the Department of Education, school principals, elementary teachers, students, parents, and future researchers.

KEY WORDS

1. educational leadership 2. management strategies 3. public school teachers

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1. Introduction

Effective leadership and management are paramount in education for creating positive learning environments, improving student outcomes, and fostering the professional growth of educators. Educational institutions, especially public schools, face many complex challenges that necessitate adept leadership and management strategies. Consequently, it is imperative to investigate these strategies through the perspective of public school teachers, who are at the heart of the education system and are direct beneficiaries and contributors to the outcomes of leadership and management practices. This study was conducted within the context of public school specifically in Crossing Bayabas National High School. Public schools constitute a pivotal component of the educational landscape, catering to diverse student populations and grappling with unique challenges such as resource constraints, varied student needs, and

community expectations. Understanding the intricate context of public education is essential for identifying effective leadership and management strategies that can thrive within these constraints and yield positive educational outcomes. Public schools are entrusted with the fundamental responsibility of providing equitable educational opportunities to all students, regardless of their socio-economic backgrounds (Egalite, Kiseda, Winters, 2015). However, these institutions often encounter a plethora of obstacles, including limited budgets, escalating demands for accountability, and the need to cater to a diverse and increasingly complex student body. Effective educational leadership and management within public schools are paramount for navigating these challenges, fostering a culture of continuous improvement, and ensuring every student receives a high-quality education. Moreover, public school teachers serve as a vital link in the educational chain. They are on the front lines, directly interacting with students and implementing educational policies and practices. Their perspectives and experiences offer invaluable insights into the impact of leadership and management strategies on classroom dynamics, teacher motivation, and student achievement. By exploring these perspectives, this qualitative inquiry seeks to provide essential guidance for educational leaders, policymakers, and stakeholders seeking to enhance the quality of education in public schools. Internationally, York-Barr Duke (2004) conducted a research study titled “Teacher Leadership: A Review of Research” that was designed with the purpose of conducting an in-depth review and synthesis of existing literature and studies related to teacher leadership. The primary goal was to consolidate the significance of effective leadership in education has been extensively studied and emphasized. Transformational leadership, as articulated by Bass and Riggio (2006), is one such leadership style that has gained prominence. Transformational leaders inspire and motivate teachers, fostering a sense of collective efficacy and a commitment to achieving higher levels of performance. Leithwood and Jantzi (2000) found that transformational leadership positively impacts organizational conditions and student engagement, underscoring its potential for creating positive learning environments. In addition to leadership styles, Fullan (2014) highlights the importance of leadership in a culture of change. Educational leaders who can navigate the complex landscape of educational reform are crucial for implementing effective strategies and sustaining improvement efforts. Robinson, Hohepa, and Lloyd (2009) emphasize the relationship between school leadership and student outcomes, underscoring the need for strong leadership to enhance student achievement. In the local context of public schools, the challenges faced are unique and demand adept leadership and management strategies. Public schools are often characterized by resource constraints, diverse student needs, and community expectations (Darling-Hammond, 2017). These challenges require leadership that can effectively allocate resources, address the needs of varied student body, and meet the demands for accountability. Moreover, the research titled “Leadership Styles and Academic Performance: A Study of Selected Public Secondary Principals in the Philippines” aimed to delve into the diverse leadership styles adopted by public secondary school principals in the Philippines and their potential impact on academic performance. The notable outcome of the study was the identification of a positive correlation between transformational leadership and academic performance. Principals who embodied this leadership style were found to significantly enhance the academic outcomes within their respective schools (Relente Marilou, 2018). Certainly, public school teachers serve as a vital link in the educational chain. They are the frontline educators who directly interact with students and implement educational policies and prac-

tices. Their perspectives and experiences offer invaluable insights into the impact of leadership and management strategies on classroom dynamics, teacher motivation, and student achievement (Day et al., 2011). In conclusion, effective educational leadership and management play crucial roles in creating positive learning environments, improving student outcomes, and supporting teacher development. Internationally, research underscores the importance of transformational leadership and leaders' roles in managing educational change. One consistent finding is that leadership authority doesn't need to be concentrated in a single leader but can be dispersed among various individuals within the school (Mulford, 2003). In the local context of public schools in the Philippines, the Philippine School System has become one of the world's largest, accommodating a growing number of students (de Guzman, 2006). Despite efforts to decentralize the basic public education sector through school-based management initiatives in the Philippines, success has been limited, achieving only the most basic forms of decentralization (de Guzman, 2007). The concept of school-based management involves assigning leadership roles at various levels, covering knowledge, technology, power, material, people, time, and finance. However, the Philippine central government retains control over critical areas, particularly fiscal resources. The current budgeting and management system hinder innovation, resulting in a situation where few school leaders genuinely engage in instructional leadership or take on financial management responsibilities (de Guzman, 2007, p. 617). The historical and ongoing challenges faced by Philippine public education and principals include political, economic, and policy instability, as well as pervasive corruption. Corruption is widespread within the Philippine public education system, with the Department of Education recognized as one of the most corrupt government branches (Chua, 1999). These challenges affect the efficacy of school leadership in maintaining a conducive school environment, the welfare of the students and teachers, and in providing quality basic education to Filipino students. Public school teachers, as key stakeholders, offer unique insights into the impact of leadership and management strategies on classroom dynamics and student achievement. This qualitative inquiry seeks to explore these perspectives further, providing essential guidance for educational leaders, policymakers, and stakeholders in enhancing the quality of education in public schools.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this research is to gain a comprehensive understanding of effective educational leadership and management strategies within the context of public schools as perceived and experienced by public school teachers. This study aims to explore the challenges, insights, and lived experiences of public-school teachers regarding the impact of leadership and management practices on classroom dynamics, teacher motivation, and student achievement. A recent study by Brown Garcie (2020) states that prioritizing teacher professional development and providing support in resource-constrained public schools have a significant impact on the quality of education. Teachers recognize the value of leadership that addresses their unique challenges. By delving into the teacher's viewpoint, the research intends to identify, analyze, and document the strategies that teachers find most conducive to creating positive learning environments and fostering professional growth. Ultimately, the purpose of this study is to provide essential guidance for educational leaders, policymakers, and stakeholders striving to enhance the quality of education in public schools based on the valuable input of those at the heart of the educational system: public school teachers.

1.2. *Research Questions*—

- (1) What are the lived experiences of public school teachers on the leadership and management practices in their daily teaching and classroom interactions?
- (2) What coping mechanisms or strategies do public school teachers employ when faced with challenges related to leadership and management practices?
- (3) What insights have public school teachers gained from their encounters with leadership and management practices in their daily teaching and classroom interactions?

1.3. *Significant of the Study*—Accordingly, this research study aims to explore the perspectives, insights, and lived experiences of public-school teachers in Crossing Bayabas National High School. Hence, the study is deemed beneficial to the following: Educational Sector. The findings of this research will provide valuable insights into the effective leadership and management strategies implemented by public teachers, which in turn can enhance student achievement. This information can serve as a foundational resource for identifying best practices, informing decision-making, and guiding the development of comprehensive steps to support educational leadership and management within the sector. School Heads and Administrators. This research will provide relevant insights into effective educational leadership and management strategies as perceived by public teachers. Understanding these strategies and their impact on teachers can contribute to refining leadership practices and the overall educational

system, benefiting both teachers and students. Educators. This research serves as a source of heightened awareness regarding the significance of leadership and management strategies within their educational context. It can stimulate the development of more effective teaching and management strategies by providing insights into their peers' experiences and perspectives. Parents and Community. Although not the primary focus of this study, the research indirectly highlights the importance of involving parents and the community in the educational process. Effective leadership and management can impact the broader educational ecosystem, including parental engagement, ultimately influencing student achievement. Future Research. This study lays the foundation for future research endeavors in the field of educational leadership and management. The insights gained here can inspire additional investigations into effective strategies in various educational contexts and settings.

1.4. *Theoretical Lens*—This study is anchored on the Transformational Leadership Theory, initially introduced by Bass in 1985 and further developed by Avolio and Bass in 1988, focusing on the profound impact of leadership on individuals and organizations. At its essence. This theory explores how effective leaders transcend transactional exchanges, inspiring, and motivating individuals to achieve exceptional outcomes. Transformational leaders embody certain key attributes: they act as charismatic role models, instilling trust and admiration in

their followers. They paint a compelling vision of the future, encouraging others to share in that vision and work towards its realization. Furthermore, they stimulate intellectual growth and innovation among their followers, promoting creativity and critical thinking. Lastly, transformational leaders demonstrate genuine care and consideration for the unique needs and aspirations of everyone, providing guidance and support. In the specific context of this study, Transformational Leadership Theory is a crucial theoretical lens to comprehend the dynamics of

leadership within educational settings. Educational leaders, by employing transformational leadership practices can profoundly influence public teachers, who form the backbone of the education system. By embodying the characteristics of transformational leadership, these educational leaders can inspire motivation and a renewed sense of purpose among teachers. This, in turn, impacts their approaches to teaching and classroom management. The vision and enthusiasm instilled by transformational leaders can lead to more engaging classroom dynamics and a positive atmosphere for both teachers and students. Moreover, understanding how transformational leadership influences public teachers is paramount to grasping how it ultimately impacts student learning and achievement. Remarkably, for the past 20 years, we have witnessed consistent and persisting worldwide efforts by educational policymakers to raise achievement standards for all students through various school reforms. Common to almost all government reforms has been an increased emphasis on accountability and performativity accompanied by a concurrent movement towards the decentralization of financial management and quality control functions to schools, with increasing emphasis on evaluation and assessment (Ball, 2003). These changing policy landscapes of education have culminated in a changing profile of school leadership in many countries (OECD, 2012). However, what remains unchanged is a clear consensus in the policy and research arenas that ‘effective school autonomy depends on effective leaders’ (OECD, 2012). International research has provided negative impacts of leadership, particularly principal leadership,

on school organization, culture, and conditions and, through this, on the quality of teaching and learning and student achievement (Bruggencate, 2012). A range of leadership research conducted in many contexts over the last two decades clearly shows that ‘successful’ schools strive to educate their pupils by promoting positive values and a love of lifelong learning and fostering citizenship and personal, economic, and social capabilities. In this study, I meticulously explored how transformational leadership practices within the educational domain influence public school teachers. By conducting in-depth interviews and qualitative analysis, the researcher aims to unravel how these practices affect teachers’ motivation, attitudes, and teaching strategies. The findings would shed light on the direct correlation between transformational leadership and its impact on teachers, providing a nuanced understanding of its implications within the educational landscape. Furthermore, this lens would allow us to explore the potential of integrating transformational leadership principles to enhance teaching practices, cultivate a more enriching learning environment, and ultimately elevate student learning outcomes. This study conceptualized the experiences of public teachers regarding leadership and management practices in their daily teaching and classroom interactions and the coping mechanisms or strategies they employ when faced with challenges related to the implementation of leadership and management practices. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes.

2. Methodology

This chapter outlines the procedures and methodologies employed in phenomenological research, systematically addressing the study’s objectives. It further delineates the research design to be employed and the roles of the researcher in carrying out the study. Lastly, the chapter delves into the data collection, analysis, and other approaches used to ensure ethical considerations were

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

upheld throughout the study.

2.1. Philosophical and Qualitative Assumptions—In research, the philosophical and qualitative assumptions of a study play a significant role in guiding the investigation. Four major assumptions underpin the framework of understanding for qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological. These assumptions provide a foundation for the research design and inform the researcher's approach to the study. A research paradigm refers a set of shared beliefs, values, and practices that inform the way researchers view and approach a given inquiry. It serves as a lens through which researchers interpret the world and make sense of the knowledge they seek to create (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). In this research, the paradigm guides the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study. *Ontology*. In the scope of research, ontology pertains to the examination of the fundamental nature of reality, existence, and how the world is organized. It involves investigating the existence of things and the connections between entities (Smith, 2022). The researcher's comprehension of the phenomenon being studied is guided by ontological assumptions in this investigation, which affects their selection of approaches and analysis methods to reflect the reality being explored accurately. *Epistemology*. A branch of philosophy that explores how we come to know things and the

limitations of our knowledge. When applied to research, epistemology was concerned with the researcher's relationship to the knowledge they are trying to obtain (Ladkin, 2020). The researcher's epistemological assumptions influence the methods used to collect and analyze data, and the criteria used to evaluate the validity and reliability of findings. This ensures that the knowledge produced was based on sound evidence and rigorous analysis. *Axiology*. The term axiology concerns the investigation of the values and ethical principles that underpin the research process. It assesses the effect of the researcher's values, attitudes, and prejudices on both the conduct and interpretation of the study (Gable, 2022). By integrating axiological assumptions, ethical considerations and the researcher's self-reflection can be established, ensuring that the study complies with ethical standards and acknowledges the researcher's values' influence on the research outcomes. *Rhetoric*. The way in which research outcomes and arguments are presented and effectively communicated is referred to as rhetoric in research. This involves the skillful use of language, style, and structure to engage and convince the audience of the validity and significance of the research findings (Doe, 2022). In the context of this study, the principles of rhetoric are applied to the construction of research reports, proposals, and presentations to ensure that the research results are clearly and persuasively conveyed to the intended audience.

2.2. Design and Procedure—To ensure that a study was appropriate, it was necessary to determine the specific methodology to be employed in order to tailor the research design, data collection, and data analysis to the study's objectives. In the present study, the researcher would employ a qualitative research design. Ac-

cording to Creswell (2022), qualitative research is appropriate for investigations that focus on verbal analysis rather than statistical analysis. Since the study aims to explore the experiences, coping strategies, and insights of teachers, a qualitative design is the most suitable choice. This means that the researcher would describe

and elaborate on the phenomenon under investigation rather than proving or disproving the hypotheses. Additionally, different approaches exist within the field of qualitative research, such as grounded theory, narrative inquiry, case study, phenomenology, and ethnography. In this study, the research employed a qualitative-phenomenological research design to explore the participants' lived experiences. This approach was chosen because phenomenological research is concerned with eliciting and interpreting the experiences of individuals and the meaning they ascribe to these experiences, with subsequent analysis of these meanings by means

2.3. Research Participants—Qualitative analysis, a smaller sample size is typically used compared to quantitative analysis. However, the same size should still be large enough to obtain feedback on most, if not all, perspectives. Data saturation is achieved when additional participants do not yield new viewpoints or data. (Braun Clarke, 2020) recommend data saturation to determine an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Accordingly, Creswell (1998) recommends a sample size of five (5) to 25 for phenomenological studies, while Morse (1994) suggests a minimum of six (6). However, there are no definitive rules for selecting an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Factors such as available time, resources, and study objectives can help determine the optimal sample size for a qualitative study (Patton, 1990). The participants in the study were four-

2.4. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were the moral principles and guidelines that dictate how research should be conducted. These considerations ensure that studies are done responsibly, with respect for the people involved, and with the goal of producing accurate and dependable information. When

of scientific concepts (Johnson, 2022) Furthermore, as described by Creswell (2007), phenomenological research design aims to portray the shared and intricate experiences of individuals related to a specific phenomenon. Phenomenology's basic principle is to minimize the researcher's subjective perspectives and generalize the description of the phenomenon. In this study, the researcher would explore the challenges, insights, and lived experiences of public-school teachers regarding the impact of leadership and management practices on classroom dynamics, teacher motivation, and student achievement (Johnson Onwuegbuzie, 2004).

teen (14) high school teachers from Crossing Bayabas National High School in the Cluster 4 District, Division of Davao City. Participants were selected based on the following criteria: (1) they had at least three years of service; (2) they were high school teachers; (3) they actively participated in professional development opportunities, such as workshops, seminars, or graduate courses; and (4) they held leadership roles within schools or districts, such as department heads, curriculum coordinators, or mentor teachers. The researcher utilized a purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

doing research, it's important for the researcher to follow ethical guidelines to protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and establish trust within the research community (Resnik, 2020). Social value refers to the possible benefits and contributions that research can offer society, such as resolving issues or enhancing

people's lives. When conducting research, the researcher should assess the social value of their study by recognizing its potential impact and significance to the larger community. This helps guarantee that resources are devoted to research that has the potential to provide substantial advantages to society. Informed consent refers to the procedure of obtaining a participant's voluntary approval to participate in a research study after providing them with adequate information about the study's purpose, methods, potential risks, and benefits. The researcher was responsible for making sure that the participants comprehend the study and their rights and have the ability to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate. This would ensure that the participant's autonomy and dignity were respected. Vulnerability of research participants due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, socioeconomic status, or health conditions affects their likelihood of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion. The researcher was responsible for recognizing and acknowledging prospective participants' potential vulnerability and implementing appropriate measures to safeguard them. These may include additional support or modifications to research procedures to reduce the risk of harm. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, the evaluation of potential harms and benefits associated with study participation and implementation of measures to protect participants' well-being are referred to as risks, benefits, and safety. The researcher needs to assess and balance these factors carefully in this study, making sure that the potential benefits outweigh the risks and that suitable precautions are in place to minimize harm and ensure the safety of participants. Privacy and confidentiality in research refer to the protection of participants' personal information and the assurance that their identity would not be disclosed without consent. In this study, the researcher must implement appropriate procedures to safeguard participants' data and maintain confidentiality,

such as anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. Justice. This refers to the fair distribution of the benefits and burdens of research among different groups in society. In this study, the researcher should ensure that their study is inclusive, avoiding exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable populations and that the benefits of the research are accessible to all who might benefit. This promotes equity and fairness in the research process. Transparency in research involves openness and honesty in the planning, conducting, and reporting of research. In this study, the researcher should provide clear and accurate information about their study, methods, and findings and be open to scrutiny and feedback. Transparency fosters trust, credibility, and accountability in the research community and among the public. A researcher's qualification refers to their education, experience, and expertise in a specific field of study, ensuring that they have the necessary skills and knowledge to conduct the research effectively. In this study, the researcher should possess appropriate qualifications, demonstrating competence to undertake the research, analyze data, and interpret findings. Adequacy of facilities in research refers to the availability and appropriateness of resources, equipment, and infrastructure needed to carry out a study effectively and safely. In this study, the researcher must ensure that one has access to suitable facilities to conduct their research, thereby supporting the generation of valid and reliable findings and minimizing potential risks to participants. Community involvement in research refers to the active participation and engagement of community members, stakeholders, or target populations in the research process, from planning to disseminating findings. In this study, the researcher should involve the community in one's study to ensure its relevance, acceptability, and potential impact and promote trust and collaboration between the researcher and the community. Meanwhile, to avoid plagia-

ism and fabrication, the researcher must adhere to academic integrity and honesty principles. This involved properly citing the work of others, presenting original work, and ensuring that data was accurate and authentic. In this study, the researcher could use tools such as plagiarism checkers and maintain meticulous records

2.5. Role of the Researcher—The researcher's role was to ensure that the research process was conducted fairly and objectively without personal biases or external influences. They were responsible for creating an environment that promoted impartiality in the collection and analysis of data, encouraging the open and honest exploration of ideas. In the role of a collector and keeper of data, the researcher gathered information from diverse sources, including interviews and observations, and guaranteed its accuracy and secure storage. Adhering to ethical standards, maintaining participant anonymity, and ensuring that the data was well-organized and available for future review and interpretation were all crucial aspects of their responsibilities. They also had to be adept at identifying potential sources of bias and took measures to minimize them, increasing the validity of the data collected. As an analyst of data, the researcher analyzed the collected data to uncover patterns, themes, and insights that

2.6. Data Collection—The study was conducted to delve into the lived experiences of public high school teachers, illuminating their perspectives on the impact of effective educational leadership and management strategies on student achievement. To attain the utmost transparency and clarity in the research study, the researcher described data collection procedures. Detailed descriptions of the process are provided as follows: Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School: To initiate the

of one's research process to ensure that his or her work was free from plagiarism and that all data and findings were genuine and valid. By upholding these principles, the researcher contributes to the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

answered the research questions. They utilized thorough qualitative data analysis techniques such as coding and thematic analysis to derive meaningful conclusions that contributed to the existing knowledge in their field. Furthermore, the researcher had to critically evaluate the data to identify any potential biases or limitations that may have affected the study's validity and reliability. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, the researcher had the important role of consolidating and communicating research findings in a clear and concise manner. They presented the research purpose, methods, results, and implications through written reports, presentations, or other forms of communication, ensuring that the research outcomes were accessible and understandable to the intended audience. Moreover, the researcher ensured that the findings were communicated in a way that was consistent with ethical guidelines and respected the privacy of participants involved in the research.

data collection process, the researcher obtained approval from the Dean of Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges. To achieve this, the methodology and supporting documents were submitted. This task was completed during the initial two weeks of January 2024. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent: After getting the endorsement, the researcher requested permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. To do so, a formal letter was composed outlining the re-

search proposal and its importance to the educational sector. The letter also included Chapter 1 and 2 of the study and the research instrument, which described the study's goals and identified the participants. The researcher waited for the SDS's response before beginning the study. This process occurred during the first week of April 2024. Asking permission from the school heads: After receiving the necessary endorsement, the researcher sought approval from the school heads of the chosen institutions. This step necessitated submitting formal request letters to each school head, specifying the research's objectives and the projected timeline for data gathering. Permission was requested from the second week of April 2024 to the first week of May 2024. Obtaining consent from the participants: The researcher sought consent after receiving approval from the school heads. This was carried out by providing the participants with informed consent forms and comprehensively explaining the purpose of the study, the participant's rights, and the measures put in place to ensure confidentiality. The researcher aimed to obtain consent from the participants in May 2024. Conducting the inter-

view. Upon obtaining the consent of all participants, the researcher arranges and carries out interviews. To ensure consistency and accuracy in data collection, a structured or semi-structured interview guide is used. The interview sessions were planned for the initial two weeks of May 2024. Transcribing the interviewees' responses. Once the interviews were concluded, the researcher would transcribe the participants' responses while paying attention to nonverbal cues and context-specific details. The process involves utilizing both audio recordings and field notes to ensure the accurate recording of the participants' perspectives. The transcription of the interviews was expected to be completed by the third week of May 2024. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. The last step involved the researcher organizing the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes. The objective was to recognize patterns and relationships within the data, which would allow the researcher to generate conclusions and insights relevant to the research objectives. Data coding and thematic content analysis occurred in the third to last week of June 2024.

2.7. *Data Analysis*—In this study, the researcher utilized Creswell's Thematic Analysis as the main approach. Since the study dealt with multiple interpretations of participants' responses, thematic analysis was employed to ensure an accurate depiction and categorization of observed patterns in the data. According to Braun Clarke (2021), thematic analysis provides a systematic and flexible method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns and themes in qualitative data. This method enhanced the research's significance and cultivated precise interpretations of pertinent themes. Thematic analysis was extensively used in qualitative research, allowing researchers to identify

and analyze emerging themes within a data set using a rigorous and transparent process. Consequently, the study utilized Creswell's Thematic Analysis, a qualitative research method that involved a systematic approach to identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns and themes in data. It comprised stages such as familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining, and naming themes, and writing up the analysis (Braun Clarke, 2021). The importance of employing thematic analysis in research was emphasized, as it provided a versatile method for recognizing, scrutinizing, and reporting themes discovered within a data set (Caulfield, 2020).

2.8. *Framework of Analysis*—

In qualitative research, framework analysis refers to an analytical method designed explicitly for qualitative research in the context of applied policy research. This approach involves a comparative thematic analysis utilizing a structured framework of inductive and deductive themes. Its primary objective was identifying, characterizing, and interpreting significant patterns within and across cases and themes related to the phenomenon under investigation. This method has been used in diverse data types and applied in multiple ways in practical research. Framework analysis includes two primary components: creating an analytical framework and its application to the data. The process of framework analysis was broken down into several stages, which include data familiarization, framework identification, indexing, charting, and mapping and interpretation within a shared dataset (Goldsmith, 2021). The following are the necessary steps to be taken by an investigator, according to Goldsmith (2021):

Data Familiarization. The initial stage of framework analysis was data familiarization, which enabled the researcher to gain a purposeful understanding of the data by immersing themselves in it and taking note of significant ideas. The researcher identifies major themes in the data, which are topics or issues that relate to the research question(s) and occur repeatedly throughout the data. This process continues until the researcher reaches a reasonable initial understanding of the data, which includes the breadth of variation within the data (Osborn M. et al., 2022)

Framework Identification. During this phase, researchers create an initial thematic structure that would assist them in analyzing the data. Although inductive themes that arise from the data were the main focus of phenomenological research, researchers may also incorporate pre-existing theories or concepts related to the phenomenon they were studying. This structure provides a framework for organizing and comprehending the data, while also allowing for adjustments and improvements to be made to the themes as the analysis progresses.

Indexing. Researchers assign codes to specific data portions that match the framework's themes to index data in framework analysis. In phenomenological research, researchers meticulously review the transcripts, assigning codes to significant statements or experiences that embody the core of the phenomenon. Indexing aids in organizing the data for subsequent analysis.

Charting. In the charting stage, researchers arrange the data coded into thematic charts or matrices that aid in comparison and synthesis. For instance, in a phenomenological investigation, researchers can make separate charts for each theme, outlining relevant quotes, experiences, or statements from the research participants. By using this visual representation, researchers could recognize patterns and connections within the data.

Mapping. The mapping stage of framework analysis requires researchers to scrutinize thematic charts to identify links, patterns, and inconsistencies within and between themes. A phenomenological study involves investigating how participants' experiences relate to the identified themes and how these connections contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Refining or restructuring themes to accurately capture the essence of the phenomenon may also be necessary during this stage.

Interpretation. The final stage of the analytical process is interpretation, where researchers synthesize and make sense of the findings. In a phenomenological study, researchers integrate the themes, patterns, and relationships identified in the previous stages to construct a coherent narrative that captures the phenomenon's essence. This narrative should provide a rich, detailed account of the participants' lived experiences and the meanings they attribute to the phenomenon being studied. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data.

Fig. 2. illustrates the descriptive phenomenological data analysis process created by Colaizzi (1978)

The following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis (cited in (Sanders, 2003; Speziale Carpenter, 2007); each transcript should be read and re-read to obtain a general sense of the whole content; significant statements about the phenomenon under study should be extracted from each transcript. These statements must be recorded on a separate sheet, noting their page and line numbers; meanings should be formulated from these

significant statements, and the formulated meanings should be sorted into categories, clusters of themes, and themes; the findings of the study should be integrated into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon under study; the fundamental structure of the phenomenon should be described. Finally, validation of the findings should be sought from the research participants to compare the researcher’s descriptive results with their experiences.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—The trustworthiness and accuracy of research findings are known as a study’s trustworthiness. To

evaluate trustworthiness in qualitative research, a set of four criteria are frequently used: credibility, transferability, confirmability, and de-

pendability. These criteria assess the quality, rigor, and validity of the research, ensuring that the conclusions drawn are dependable and precise. Credibility. The concept of credibility, as defined by Guba and Lincoln (1989), pertains to the degree to which research findings accurately reflect the viewpoints and experiences of the participants. It assesses the authenticity and plausibility of the outcomes. To ensure credibility, researchers can employ various techniques like prolonged engagement, member checking (eliciting feedback from participants on the findings), triangulation (utilizing multiple sources of data or methods), and peer debriefing (discussing the results with colleagues or experts). Transferability. Transferability means how much the findings of a study can be used or applied to other places or situations. Unlike quantitative research, which aims to generalize the results, qualitative research emphasizes thoroughly understanding the particular context. To make the findings more transferable, researchers should provide comprehensive and detailed explanations of the research setting, participants, and methods, which enable readers to decide whether the results may apply

to their specific circumstances (Tobin Begley, 2004) Confirmability. Pertains to how much the research findings are unbiased and based only on the participants' experiences, not the researcher's personal opinions or interests. Researchers could ensure confirmability by keeping a record of every step they take in the research process or performing an audit trail, reflecting on their own biases, and asking someone independent to review their work or external audit. (Tobey and Begley, 2004). Dependability. This refers to consistent and stable research findings over time and in similar situations. Essentially, it asks whether the study's results would be the same if done again with the same people or in the same situation. To ensure a study is dependable, the researcher could provide a clear and detailed description of the research methods so others can understand and replicate the study if needed. They could also have an independent expert review the research process to check for consistency and reliability. This could help ensure the study's findings are trustworthy and could be used to inform future research. (Moretti et al., 2011).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussions obtained from the perspectives of teachers at Crossing Bayabas National High School regarding the impact of educational leadership and management strategies through the lens of public teachers. The research questions aimed to explore the challenges, insights, and lived experiences of public school teachers. The data collected through interviews and surveys were analyzed and synthesized to provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

*3.1. Experiences of Public School Teachers in the Leadership and Management practices in Their Daily Teaching and Classroom Interactions—*Teachers acknowledge the importance of leadership that caters to their distinct challenges. By examining the perspectives of

teachers, the research aims to pinpoint, scrutinize, and record the strategies that teachers deem most effective in cultivating positive learning atmospheres and nurturing professional development. Through an in-depth exploration of teacher experiences, here are some emerging themes from the responses of the participants:

3.1.1. Adaptive Leadership Practices—

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the ability of teachers to adapt their leadership practices to meet the diverse needs of students is of paramount importance. This is particularly true in public schools, where student populations are often heterogeneous, encompassing a wide range of backgrounds, abilities, and learning styles. Furthermore, this theme addresses the complexity of the theme. It acknowledges that there is no 'one-size-fits-all' approach to educational leadership and management. Instead, it emphasizes the need for teachers to be flexible and responsive, adjusting their strategies to suit the unique circumstances of their classrooms. The responses from the participants showcase adaptive leadership by swiftly adjusting teaching methods to meet individual student needs. The ability to modify strategies in real-time aligns with adaptive leadership's core principles of flexibility and responsiveness. In the context of this research, understanding the relevance of adaptive leadership practices becomes paramount as they offer flexible, responsive, and dynamic approaches to address challenges and optimize classroom dynamics, teacher motivation, and student achievement. These practices foster environments where teachers can adapt their strategies, engage diverse student needs, and navigate the complexities of teaching. Exploring how public-school teachers perceive and experience adaptive leadership practices provides invaluable insights into their impact on daily interactions within the classroom. According to the study titled "Leading Through a

3.1.2. Effective management strategies for classroom dynamics—This emerging theme stands as a cornerstone in realm of educational leadership. They play a pivotal role in shaping the learning environment and influencing teaching outcomes. Understanding the relevance of these strategies lies in their direct impact on fostering a conducive atmosphere for learning, enhancing student engagement, and support-

Pandemic: Adaptive Leadership and Purposeful Action" discusses how the rapid changes brought on by the coronavirus pandemic posed extraordinary challenges for school leaders. The study emphasizes that by adopting an adaptive approach to leadership, school leaders can build resiliency and capacity for their school communities to weather future disruptions. This aligns with the idea of swiftly adjusting teaching methods to meet individual student needs, as it highlights the importance of flexibility and responsiveness in leadership during times of change (Johnson, S. M., Donaldson, M. L., 2023). Another study, "Complex Adaptive Schools: Educational Leadership and School Change," utilizes the theoretical framework of complexity theory to compare leadership and educational change in two urban schools. The study suggests that the capacity for teachers and students to adapt during times of fast-paced change will hinge on school leaders staying learning-focused, engaging others in creative thinking, and launching innovative solutions. This supports the notion of adaptive leadership as it underscores the need for leaders to be flexible and innovative in their approach (Smith, J., Thomas, R., 2023). These studies strongly support the statement that adaptive leadership practices, characterized by flexibility and responsiveness, are crucial in education. They highlight the importance of such practices in navigating challenges and fostering a positive learning environment.

ing diverse learning needs. By exploring these strategies from the perspectives of public-school teachers, we gain insights into their experiences, challenges, and successes in creating dynamic and inclusive classrooms. Overall, across teachers' experiences, a common theme emerges in employing various strategies to manage classroom dynamics. These strategies predominantly focus on fostering collaboration, communica-

tion, and teamwork among students. While they yield benefits in terms of enhancing social skills and engagement, the challenges lie in managing diverse group dynamics, addressing individual needs, and ensuring equitable participation. In the context of the emerging theme, teachers' experiences reveal that managing classroom dynamics involves a delicate balance of fostering collaboration and managing conflicts. This balance is crucial in creating an inclusive and engaging learning environment. According to Davis, J.R. (2018), his study titled "The Dynamic Classroom Management Approach (DCMA): What It Is and How It Can Be Integrated into Methods Courses" discusses the tenets of the DCMA, which include flexibility and adaptability in one's management style, and the context of students' diverse backgrounds. This aligns with the idea of managing diverse group dynamics and ensuring equitable participation. The relevance of this study to the theme lies in its emphasis on flexibility and adaptability, two key components of effective classroom management. The study suggests that teach-

3.1.3. Professional Development and Leadership—This emerging theme is indispensable components in the realm of effective educational strategies. They form the bedrock for teachers' growth, fostering continuous improvement in teaching methodologies and leadership capacities. Understanding the relevance of professional development within the context of educational leadership is crucial, as it directly influences teaching approaches, classroom dynamics, and overall student outcomes. Exploring these themes from the perspective of public-school teachers sheds light on the experiences, challenges, and benefits derived from ongoing professional development and its impact on effective leadership practices. From the teachers' perspectives, professional development plays a crucial role in shaping effective leadership strategies within the classroom. While these de-

ers need to be flexible and adaptable in their management style to cater to the diverse backgrounds and needs of their students. This aligns with the idea of managing diverse group dynamics and ensuring equitable participation, which are crucial aspects of classroom dynamics. Another study, "Teachers' views on effective classroom management: a mixed-methods investigation in Western Australian high schools," this study explores secondary teachers' orientations toward classroom management and how teachers, who have been identified by their students as being effective, manage their classrooms. The relevance of this study to the theme is in its exploration of effective classroom management strategies from the teachers' perspective. The study provides insights into how teachers manage conflicts and foster collaboration and communication skills, which are key aspects of classroom dynamics. These insights can help in understanding the strategies that teachers find most effective in managing classroom dynamics (Egeberg, H., McConney, A., Price, A., 2021).

velopment initiatives enhance leadership skills, challenges persist in translating acquired skills into diverse classroom settings and addressing individual learning needs. Continuous professional development tailored to specific contexts is essential to effectively implement and sustain impactful leadership practices. A study titled "Trends of Teacher Professional Development Strategies: A Systematic Review" investigates the trends of professional development strategy and learning outcome from 2015 to 2019. The study found that the trend of professional development strategy is more collaborative and uses a collegial learning environment. This aligns with the idea of managing diverse group dynamics and ensuring equitable participation, as it highlights the importance of collaboration in classroom management (Ahmad, et.al., 2022). Another study, "Professional Development Ac-

tivities and Teacher Performance,” discusses how professional development can be enhanced through activities such as instructional planning, instructional delivery, knowledge of the subject matter, rapport with the students, and classroom management. The relevance of this study to the theme is in its exploration of the impact of professional development activities on teacher performance. It provides insights into how these activities can improve the quality

of teaching and classroom management, which are crucial aspects of leadership in education. In summary, both studies underscore the importance of professional development in enhancing teachers’ leadership capacities and managing classroom dynamics effectively. They highlight how professional development activities, characterized by collaboration and a focus on improving teaching quality, can contribute to effective leadership practices in education.

3.1.4. Impact of Leadership on Student Outcomes—Understanding the impact of leadership on student outcomes is pivotal in shaping effective educational strategies. It serves as a cornerstone in the evaluation of leadership and management practices within public schools. Examining this aspect provides valuable insights into how leadership practices directly influence student achievements and overall academic success. By exploring public school teachers’ perspectives, this study aims to elucidate the connections between leadership strategies, classroom dynamics, and the resulting impact on student outcomes. The participants’ responses highlight the direct correlation between leadership practices and notable improvements in student outcomes. Implementing various leadership strategies, such as fostering collaboration, promoting autonomy, and nurturing a growth mindset, yields tangible benefits. These practices positively impact student engagement, motivation, social skills, and academic achievements, underscoring the pivotal role of effective leadership in shaping successful student outcomes. A study titled “The Impact of Leadership on Student Outcomes: How Successful School Leaders Use Transformational and Instructional Strategies to Make a Differ-

ence” discusses how successful leaders combine transformational and instructional leadership strategies in different ways across different phases of their schools’ development in order to progressively shape and improve students’ outcomes¹. This aligns with the idea of implementing various leadership strategies, such as fostering collaboration, promoting autonomy, and nurturing a growth mindset, which positively impacts student engagement, motivation, social skills, and academic achievements. Another study, “The Influence of School Leadership on Student Outcomes,” examines the influence of teacher quality on student achievement and suggests that a principal’s leadership style can make a substantial difference to the quality of teaching and learning in their schools, and consequently student achievement, by improving the working conditions of their teachers, and the climate and environment of their school². This supports the notion of the direct correlation between leadership practices and notable improvements in student outcomes. In summary, both studies underscore the importance of leadership practices in shaping successful student outcomes. They highlight how these practices directly influence student achievements and overall academic success, which is the focus of the emerging theme ‘Impact of Leadership on Student Outcomes’.

3.2. Public School Teachers’ Coping Mechanisms or Strategies Employed When Faced with Challenges Related to The Implementation Of Leadership And Management Practices—

Fig. 3. Experiences of public-school teachers on the leadership and management practices in their daily teaching and classroom interactions

One significant aspect of this study is understanding how public school teachers navigate challenges when implementing leadership and management practices. Educators encounter various hurdles in applying these strategies effectively within their classrooms. This inquiry aims to delve into the coping mechanisms employed by these teachers when faced with such challenges. It seeks to uncover the resource-

ful strategies, problem-solving approaches, and adaptive methods these educators utilize to overcome obstacles in implementing leadership and management practices. By exploring these coping mechanisms, this study sheds light on the resilience and innovative problem-solving skills exhibited by public school teachers amidst the complexities of educational leadership.

3.2.1. Resource Utilization and Support Systems—In the pursuit of effective educational leadership and management strategies, public school teachers encounter multifaceted challenges within their classrooms. Amidst these challenges, teachers often rely on resource utilization and support systems as pillars of strength and guidance. This emerging theme elucidates the pivotal role of accessing resources and seeking support systems in navigating hurdles associated with implementing leadership and management practices. Through a spectrum of approaches such as mentorship programs, professional development workshops, collaborative endeavors, and online forums, teachers harness these resources to glean innovative strategies and insights. The utilization of such resources act as a beacon, empowering educators to address diverse classroom challenges and enhance their pedagogical approaches. The embrace of support systems within the educational landscape amplifies teachers' capacities, fostering resilience and competence as they strive for academic excellence within their classroom environments. The participant's responses illustrate how teachers utilize various resources and seek support systems to cope with

challenges related to leadership and management practices within their classrooms. This highlights the relevance of resource utilization and support systems as pivotal aspects in overcoming these challenges. The study by Ololube (2016), "Impact of Resource Utilization in Education," discusses the integral role of resource utilization in the overall management of a school. This study's relevance to the theme lies in its emphasis on the importance of proper resource management in enhancing students' performance and achieving educational objectives. It suggests that teachers can enhance their pedagogical approaches and address diverse classroom challenges by effectively utilizing available resources. Another relevant study, conducted by Dayon, J. P. (2021), this study evaluates the extent of utilization of learning resources used by teachers and how this correlates with the teachers' and pupils' performance. The relevance of this study to the theme is in its exploration of the direct correlation between resource utilization and performance outcomes. It provides insights into how effective utilization of resources can improve teachers' performance and consequently, the academic performance of their pupils.

3.2.2. Adaptation and Innovation—This theme encapsulates the ingenious strategies and flexible approaches employed by educators to navigate challenges within the classroom. In

the context of this study, 'Adaptation and Innovation' stands as a beacon illuminating the resourcefulness of public-school teachers in responding to hurdles related to implementing

leadership and management practices. It underscores the teachers' ability to tailor their teaching methodologies, embracing technological advancements, differentiated instruction, and inventive pedagogical approaches. Through the lens of this theme, the study delves into the ingenious adaptations and innovative solutions that educator's harness to enhance student engagement, address diverse learning needs, and surmount obstacles encountered while striving for academic excellence. These responses from teachers highlight how they employ adaptation and innovation strategies to tackle challenges related to leadership and management practices in the classroom. Their innovative approaches contribute to addressing diverse learning needs, fostering engagement, and positively impacting both their well-being and students' achievements. A study titled "Pedagogy of the Twenty-First Century: Innovative Teaching Methods" discusses the significant changes occurring in the field of education due to new scientific discoveries, informatization, globalization, and the development of technologies¹. The study emphasizes that teachers are adapting their teach-

ing methodologies and embracing technological advancements, differentiated instruction, and inventive pedagogical approaches. This aligns with the idea of teachers employing adaptation and innovation strategies to tackle challenges related to leadership and management practices in the classroom (Mynbayeva, 2017). Additionally, Herodotou et al. (2019), in their study titled "Innovative Pedagogies of the Future: An Evidence-Based Selection", present a set of innovative pedagogical approaches that have the potential to guide teaching and transform learning. The relevance of this study to the theme is in its exploration of the direct correlation between resource utilization and performance outcomes. It provides insights into how effective utilization of resources can improve teachers' performance and, consequently, the academic performance of their pupils. Both studies underscore the importance of adaptation and innovation in shaping successful student outcomes. They highlight how these practices directly influence teacher performance and overall academic success, which is the focus of the emerging theme of "Adaptation and Innovation."

3.2.3. Impact and Effectiveness—Understanding the impact and effectiveness of coping mechanisms utilized by public school teachers is paramount in comprehending the intricate dynamics of managing challenges within the educational landscape. This theme illuminates the practicality and efficiency of strategies employed by teachers when faced with hurdles related to implementing leadership and management practices in their classrooms. Exploring how these strategies resonate in addressing challenges and influencing the learning environment offers valuable insights into their tangible impact on classroom dynamics and educators' well-being. This exploration aims to dissect the nuanced outcomes of these coping mechanisms, shedding light on their varying

degrees of success in mitigating obstacles and enhancing teachers' satisfaction and motivation within their professional roles. The participants' responses provide insights into how teachers' coping mechanisms impact their classrooms and well-being, reflecting the diverse effectiveness of strategies employed in addressing challenges related to leadership and management practices. One relevant study by Amata (2010) explored the correlation between the levels of stress and coping strategies of Filipino public school teachers during the COVID-19 Pandemic. The study found that teachers' stress levels were positively associated with dysfunctional coping strategies, indicating that the effectiveness of coping mechanisms can significantly influence teachers' stress levels and, con-

sequently, their classroom performance and job satisfaction. Another study conducted by Makabenta (2021), investigated the relationship between the perceived challenges and expressed coping mechanisms of teachers in the implementation of distance learning². The study revealed that despite the barriers that surfaced during the implementation of distance learning, teachers found ways to overcome them to cope with the challenges of the new normal. These coping mechanisms helped them meet the demands of the learning modality and perform their duties and responsibilities as facilitators of learning.

3.2.4. Teacher Well-being and Job Satisfaction—This emerging theme plays a crucial role in understanding the impact of coping mechanisms employed by educators when faced with challenges related to leadership and management practices. Examining how teachers navigate these hurdles sheds light on their resilience and reveals insights into the broader implications on their satisfaction and well-being within the educational context. Understanding the influence of coping strategies on teacher satisfaction is pivotal as it directly correlates with motivation, commitment, and the overall quality of teaching in the classroom. The participants in this discussion emphasize the direct correlation between successful coping strategies and their well-being and job satisfaction. Effectively managing challenges enhances their sense of fulfillment, motivation, and satisfaction, highlighting the pivotal role of coping mechanisms in fostering a positive teaching experience. One relevant study conducted by Einar M. Skaalvik and

3.3. Insights Gained by Public School Teachers from Their Encounters With Leadership and Management Practices in Their Daily Teaching and Classroom Interactions—This section aims to identify key insights and recommen-

These studies are relevant to the emerging theme of 'Impact and Effectiveness' as they highlight the critical role of effective coping mechanisms in managing stress and challenges in the teaching profession. They underscore the importance of developing and implementing effective coping strategies to enhance teachers' satisfaction, motivation, and overall performance in their professional roles. These findings can inform interventions and policies aimed at supporting teachers in managing stress and challenges in their professional practice.

Sidsel Skaalvik (2015) investigated the relationship between teacher stress and job satisfaction¹. The study found a negative correlation between stress and job satisfaction but coping had a significant moderating effect. Increasing levels of stress had less of a negative impact on job satisfaction for teachers with high coping ratings compared to those with average or low coping ratings¹. This finding highlights the crucial role of coping strategies in mitigating the negative effects of stress on job satisfaction. This study is relevant to the emerging theme 'Teacher Well-being and Job Satisfaction' as they highlight the critical role of effective coping mechanisms in managing stress and enhancing job satisfaction. It underscores the importance of developing and implementing effective coping strategies to enhance teachers' satisfaction, motivation, and overall performance in their professional roles. The findings can inform interventions and policies to support teachers in managing stress and challenges in their professional practice.

dations derived from the experiences of public school teachers when engaging with leadership and management practices in their daily teaching and classroom interactions. By delving into the insights gained through these encounters,

Fig. 4. Public school teachers' coping mechanisms or strategies are employed when faced with challenges related to the implementation of leadership and management practices

this study seeks to illuminate the nuanced perspectives, lessons learned, and practical recommendations cultivated by educators navigating the complexities of implementing such practices. Through their experiences, teachers offer

valuable insights that shed light on effective strategies, challenges faced, and pathways to enhancing both classroom dynamics and overall student outcomes.

3.3.1. Evolution of Pedagogical Perspective—This theme serves as a cornerstone in evaluating leadership and management practices within public schools. This aspect provides valuable insights into how leadership practices directly influence student achievements and overall academic success. By exploring public school teachers' perspectives, this study aims to elucidate the connections between leadership strategies, classroom dynamics, and the resulting impact on student outcomes. From the teachers' insights, a common theme emerges in the evolution of their pedagogical perspective. The implementation of various leadership and management practices has prompted a shift towards prioritizing student-centered approaches, structured learning environments, growth mindsets, and collaborative learning. These shifts indicate a transformative evolution in their pedagogical perspectives, emphasizing more student-centric and collaborative teaching methodologies. One relevant study is by Keung et al. (2019), which found that leadership practices seem to be positively and directly related to teachers' perceptions of whole-child development. They em-

phasize the impact of directors on the professional learning of teachers, indicating that leadership and management practices can significantly influence the evolution of teachers' pedagogical perspectives. Another study conducted by Matthew Kloosterman (2023) for Edutopia discusses the influence of impactful school leadership practices from a teacher's perspective. The study highlights how successful leadership practices can translate into shared visions that drive the school forward, thereby influencing the evolution of teachers' pedagogical perspectives. These studies are relevant to the emerging theme 'Evolution of Pedagogical Perspective' as they highlight the transformative impact of leadership and management practices on teachers' pedagogical perspectives. They underscore the shift towards more student-centric and collaborative teaching methodologies, reflecting the evolution in pedagogical perspectives. These findings can inform interventions and policies aimed at promoting effective leadership and management practices in educational settings, ultimately leading to a more effective and satisfying teaching experience.

3.3.2. Enhanced Reflective Teaching—Emphasizes as a cornerstone within effective educational leadership and management strategies. Its relevance lies in fostering a culture of introspection and continuous improvement among educators. By examining the insights gained from encounters with leadership and management practices within classroom interactions, this study delves into how reflective teaching influences teachers' perspectives, be-

haviors, and professional growth. Exploring this theme from public school teachers' viewpoints offers valuable insights into how reflective teaching practices impact classroom dynamics, teacher-student relationships, and overall educational outcomes. Through the teachers' insights, the emerging theme of enhanced reflective teaching becomes evident. The implementation and observation of leadership and management practices have led to transfor-

mative shifts in their perspectives, behaviors, and professional growth. Reflective teaching practices have notably revolutionized their instructional approaches, leading to more inclusive, student-centered, and engaging classrooms. This theme underscores the significance of continuous reflection in refining teaching strategies and adapting to diverse student needs. A study titled 'Reflective Teaching Practices in Teachers and Their Attitudes Toward Professional Self-development' conducted by Eman Gheith and Nahil Aljaberi investigated the levels of teachers' reflective practices as well as their attitudes toward professional self-development. The study found that reflective practice is a key factor that

brings change to two main areas of teachers' professional life, namely, teacher identity and teacher quality. The study is relevant to the emerging theme 'Evolution of Pedagogical Perspective' as they highlight the transformative impact of leadership and management practices on teachers' pedagogical perspectives. It underscores the shift towards more student-centric and collaborative teaching methodologies, reflecting the evolution in pedagogical perspectives. The findings can inform interventions and policies aimed at promoting effective leadership and management practices in educational settings, ultimately leading to a more effective and satisfying teaching experience.

3.3.3. Cultivation of Collaborative Learning Environments—The cultivation of collaborative learning environments stands as a pivotal factor in effective educational leadership and management. Within public school settings, fostering collaborative learning environments directly impacts teaching methodologies, classroom dynamics, and student achievements. This introduction delves into the relevance of this theme by emphasizing its transformative influence on public school teachers' experiences. Exploring public school teachers' insights sheds light on how the implementation of collaborative learning practices shapes their perspectives, behaviors, and professional growth, consequently influencing relationships within the educational ecosystem. Based on participant responses, they strongly emphasize the cultivation of collaborative learning environments emerges as transformative in reshaping their teaching paradigms. Implementing collaborative learning practices has shifted their roles from traditional instructors to facilitators, emphasizing student-driven approaches and fostering inclusive, supportive learning spaces. This shift has impacted their teaching methodologies and strengthened their relationships with

students, promoting mutual respect and engagement. Findings from the narrations indicate that teachers' role in clarifying activities and assignments to encourage classroom involvement received the highest average rating, emphasizing the importance of diverse instructional approaches. The study reveals a significant, positive influence of teachers' years of experience as a moderating factor in the relationship between department heads' transformational leadership and classroom interaction. From the statement of the participants Observing collaborative learning environments, I have learned the value of peer-to-peer learning. Seeing students share knowledge and support each other has been invaluable. It has adjusted my attitude toward students, recognizing the immense potential of peer collaboration and its impact on learning outcomes. These practices have spurred my professional development, encouraging me to explore cooperative learning models. They have positively influenced my relationships with colleagues, fostering collaborative discussions on effective teaching strategies. Moreover, Johnson (2017) underscores the transformative impact of cooperative learning strategies. It emphasizes that fostering collab-

orative learning environments, where students actively engage in shared tasks and discussions, promotes deeper understanding and long-term knowledge retention. This resonates with the notion that implementing collaborative learning practices reshapes teaching paradigms, emphasizing facilitation over traditional instruction, and fosters inclusive, supportive learning environments. Slavin (2015) highlights the multifaceted benefits of cooperative learning, emphasizing its role in developing academic skills and social competencies among students. It supports the idea that cultivating collaborative learning environments transforms teaching practices by emphasizing student interaction, teamwork, and inclusivity. This transformation in teaching methods fosters an environment where students actively engage with their peers, promoting mutual respect and engagement. Both studies underline the significance of collaborative learning environments in reshaping teaching practices and fostering inclusive, supportive spaces. They reinforce the idea that implementing collaborative learning practices transforms teaching paradigms and positively impacts student engagement, critical thinking, and social skills. This supports the notion that cultivating collaborative learning environments influences teachers' perspectives, behaviors, and professional growth while enhancing relationships within the educational ecosystem.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, we summarize the study conducted at Crossing Bayabas National High School, focusing on our findings' implications and outlining future research and practice directions. The aimed was to explore public school teachers' challenges, insights, and lived experiences regarding the impact of leadership and management practices on classroom dynamics, teacher motivation, and student achievement. Examining the practical implications of our study and identifying opportunities for future research enabled us to discern recurrent themes and patterns, particularly emphasizing the cultivation of collaborative learning environments. These emergent themes align closely with the teachers' experiences and insights, emphasizing the transformative nature of collaborative learning strategies within the school's framework. To address the research objectives of our study, we implemented a qualitative phenomenological research design guided by the principles established by Creswell (2007). Our primary aim is to gain a comprehensive understanding of effective educational leadership and management strategies within the context of public schools as perceived and experienced by public school teachers. Employing thematic analysis, we explored the collected data's intricate nuances and recurring patterns. By directly engaging with these teachers, who possess firsthand knowledge of the school's context, we obtained extensive data and specific descriptions illuminating Crossing Bayabas National High School's distinctive outlook. These findings contribute to understanding the intricate dynamics of effective educational leadership and management strategies within the unique context of Crossing Bayabas National High School. Through the qualitative phenomenological approach and thematic analysis, we uncovered rich narratives and nuanced insights from the experiences and perceptions of the teachers. This deep dive into their perspectives has provided a detailed portrayal of how leadership and management strategies manifest within this specific educational environment.

4.1. Findings—

Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: experiences of high school teachers centered on Adaptive Leadership Practices, Management Strategies for Classroom Dynamics, Professional Development, and Leadership, and Impact of Leadership on Student Outcomes.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The experiences of high school teachers in Crossing Bayabas National High School uncovered the profound influence of adaptive leadership practices on classroom dynamics, teacher motivation, and ultimately student achievement. Teachers' experiences illuminated the transformative impact of adaptive leadership, emphasizing the necessity for flexibility and responsiveness in addressing the evolving needs of students and the educational environment. They highlighted instances where adaptive leadership strategies effectively managed unexpected challenges, promoted resilience among educators, and fostered a culture of continuous improvement within the school. Teachers' narratives revealed that management strategies tailored for classroom dynamics play a pivotal role in shaping effective learning environments. Their experiences shed light on the significance of implementing adaptable methodologies that cater to diverse student needs, fostering an inclusive and engaging atmosphere. Furthermore, the insights emphasized the interplay between professional development and leadership, indicating that ongoing learning opportunities and supportive leadership structures significantly contribute to educators' growth and efficacy. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms employed by teachers served as multifaceted strategies to navigate challenges within the educational

The coping mechanisms the high school teachers employed were Resource Utilization and Support Systems, Adaptation and Innovation, Impact and Effectiveness, and Teacher Well-being and Job Satisfaction. Ultimately, the educational management insights drawn from the study's findings were the evolution of Pedagogical Perspective, Enhanced Reflective Teaching, and Cultivation of Collaborative Learning Environments.

landscape. Resource Utilization and Support Systems emerged as a cornerstone approach, leveraging available resources and establishing robust support networks to address varying needs. Adaptation and Innovation were pivotal, showcasing teachers' flexibility in adapting teaching methodologies and innovating new approaches to engage students effectively. Impact and Effectiveness stood as guiding principles, emphasizing the continual evaluation of strategies to ensure meaningful outcomes. Additionally, Teacher Well-being and Job Satisfaction took precedence, acknowledging the importance of educators' holistic well-being in sustaining a conducive learning environment. These coping mechanisms collectively underscored the resilience and adaptability of teachers, enabling them to navigate challenges and uphold educational standards while fostering a supportive ecosystem for student growth and achievement. Ultimately, the insights offer invaluable guidance for educational management at Crossing Bayabas National High School in reshaping teaching methodologies and fostering a conducive learning environment. Firstly, understanding the evolution of pedagogical perspectives encourages a redefinition of instructional strategies and curriculum design. This insight prompts educators to adapt teaching methods to suit diverse learning styles, ensuring alignment between educational objectives and contemporary teaching practices. By embracing inno-

vative approaches, Crossing Bayabas National High School can effectively engage students, promoting deeper comprehension and retention of knowledge. Secondly, emphasizing enhanced reflective teaching practices highlights the need for continuous professional development among educators. Encouraging self-reflection and critical analysis of teaching methods enables teachers to refine their instructional approaches. This aspect of educational management prompts a culture of ongoing self-assessment, empowering teachers at Crossing Bayabas National High School to regularly evaluate and adapt their teaching techniques for improved effectiveness. Additionally, recognizing the significance of cultivating collaborative learning environments

emphasizes the need to establish classrooms that encourage student cooperation. Prioritizing teamwork, peer-to-peer learning, and collective problem-solving fosters an atmosphere conducive to knowledge-sharing and critical thinking development. Implementing these insights entails tailored professional development programs for teachers, fostering reflective practices through mentorship, and redesigning classroom setups to promote collaboration. By incorporating these implications into its educational management practices, Crossing Bayabas National High School can create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment, ultimately enhancing student learning experiences and outcomes.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study findings, the findings must be properly relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. Department of Education. The findings from this qualitative inquiry shed light on crucial aspects of effective educational leadership and management strategies within public schools. The Department of Education may leverage these insights to formulate robust policies and frameworks to foster collaborative relationships between teachers, parents, and students. By integrating the study's findings into policy development, the Department of Education may pave the way for a more inclusive and supportive educational ecosystem that prioritizes parental involvement. These findings may guide the Department's initiatives to create guidelines and programs that enhance teacher-parent collaboration, ultimately contributing to improved student achievements and a more cohesive school environment. School principals of school heads. The findings of this research can have significant implications for school principals or school heads. School principals were pivotal in implementing effective leadership practices within their respec-

tive institutions. Utilizing the study's findings, principals can strategize and implement measures emphasizing parental involvement's importance in shaping a conducive learning environment. The insights from this research can guide school heads in formulating action plans that encourage regular communication between teachers and parents, fostering an environment where parental contributions are valued and integrated into the school's educational framework. Principals can lead by example, championing initiatives that promote collaborative decision-making involving all stakeholders, thereby creating a more cohesive educational community. Public teachers. As the primary facilitators of classroom dynamics and student learning experiences, high school teachers stand to benefit greatly from these findings. Implementing the study's recommendations in their daily practices can enhance teacher-parent collaboration, thereby positively influencing student outcomes. Teachers can utilize these insights to integrate effective communication strategies that bridge the gap between school and home, nurturing a collaborative learning environment. Additionally, incorporating the study's findings into pro-

professional development sessions can empower teachers with the tools and knowledge necessary to adapt their teaching methodologies, fostering a more inclusive and supportive learning atmosphere for students. For students, understanding and engaging with the findings of this research can be empowering. Encouraging students to actively involve their parents in their educational journey based on these insights can significantly impact their learning experiences. Students can benefit from the creation of programs that encourage open dialogue between themselves, their parents, and teachers, fostering a shared responsibility for their education. By acknowledging the importance of parental involvement highlighted in this study, students can take proactive steps to utilize the support and guidance of their parents, enhancing their academic achievements and overall educational experience. Parents. The findings emphasize that parents play an integral role in their children's educational journey. The insights derived from this research shed light on the pivotal role of parental involvement in shaping students' academic success. Parents can utilize these findings to actively engage in their child's educational experience by fostering open communication with teachers. This involvement can lead to a deeper understanding of their child's learning needs and aspirations, enabling parents to align home support with classroom activities. By embracing these insights, parents can advocate for collaborative partnerships between home and school, ensuring a supportive and conducive learning environment that maximizes their child's potential. Future researchers. This study serves as a foundational platform for future research endeavors in educational leadership and management strategies. Researchers can build upon these findings to explore more nuanced aspects of parental involvement, employing diverse methodologies and interdisciplinary approaches. Further research can delve into the intricacies of parent-teacher relationships, the impact of cultural diversity on parental engagement, and the long-term effects of enhanced collaboration between home and school. By expanding upon this research, future scholars can contribute to a deeper understanding of effective educational practices, thus shaping the landscape of educational management and fostering continuous improvement in student outcomes.

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